

**A CASE STUDY ON PRASRAMSINI YONIVYAPAD: EVIDENCE-BASED AYURVEDIC
APPROACH TO PELVIC ORGAN PROLAPSE**Alfiya Patel^{1*}, Amrutha B. S.²

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ABSTRACT

Prasramsini Yoni Vyapada, described in Ayurvedic classics, is downward displacement or laxity of the vaginal wall structures accompanied by symptoms such as urinary incontinence, incomplete bladder emptying, lower abdominal heaviness and discomfort. It can correlate with conditions like uterine prolapse, cystocele and pelvic floor weakness. This case study presents the Ayurvedic clinical management of a 50-year-old female patient presenting with urinary incontinence, sensation of incomplete bladder emptying and white discharge P/v associated with lower abdominal heaviness and low back ache and on per vaginal examination, signs of anterior vaginal wall laxity noted and diagnosed as 2nd degree Cystocele and 1st degree uterine prolapse. Yoni Prakshalana with Nimbamritadi kashaya and Yoni Pichu with Nalpamaradi and Changeryadi gritham was administered for seven days. Complete resolution of significant symptoms was observed, along with improvement in objective parameters. This report highlights the scope of Ayurvedic interventions in managing Prasramsini Yonivyapad (Pelvic organ Prolapse).

KEYWORDS: Complete resolution of significant symptoms was observed, along with improvement in objective parameters.

INTRODUCTION

In Ayurveda, *Yoni Vyapada* encompasses twenty types of gynaecological disorders, among which *Prasramsini*^[1] is characterized by laxity of pelvic structures leading to protrusion or bulging of the vaginal wall. Acharyas describe features such as pelvic discomfort, heaviness, pain radiating to the back and lower limbs, and urinary disturbances.

Modern correlations include pelvic organ prolapse^[2], and pelvic floor dysfunction which are the conditions common among multiparous and postmenopausal women due to ligamentous weakness and increased intra-abdominal pressure.

Ayurvedic management focuses on strengthening pelvic tissues (*yonibalya*), reducing inflammation, and promoting normal function of *vata dosha* through internal and external therapies. Sthanika Chikitsa like *Yoni Prakshalana* (vaginal cleansing) and *Yoni Pichu* (therapeutic tamponing) are key procedures indicated in such conditions.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

- To evaluate the effectiveness of Ayurvedic local therapies— *Yoni Pichu* and *Yoni Prakshalana*—in the management of *Prasramsini Yonivyapada* (pelvic organ prolapse)

- To document clinical improvement in symptoms associated with anterior vaginal wall laxity and Urinary incontinence.

LMP- 06/12/2025
 PLMP- 05/08/2025
 Nature- Regular 3days/30days

CASE REPORT

Case Presentation

A 50-year-old married female patient, a homemaker residing in Kanchipuram, presented with complaints of dribbling of urine on and off, a sensation of incomplete bladder emptying, with lower abdominal heaviness and lower back pain radiating towards bilateral lower limb since 3 years. She is also complaining of intermittent curdy white discharge per vaginum on and off without vulval itching for the past 10 years. Urinary incontinence increases during coughing, sneezing and standing for long time. She didn't take any treatment for the same. Patient took treatment for white discharge P/V and there is recurrence after stoppage of medication. As both the conditions became worse, she approached the OPD of department of PTSR, SJSACH for further treatment.

Past History

- Varicose veins for 10 years
- No H/o HTN/DM/Asthma /Thyroid dysfunction

Past Treatment History

Nothing significant.

Previous Surgical History

- Appendectomy in 2014
- Lower segment caesarean section (LSCS) -3 TIMES.

Family History

Nothing significant.

Menstrual History

Menarche – 14 yrs of age
 Menopause – not attained

Treatment Protocol

Day-wise Treatment Chart

Procedure Details

Date	Treatment given	Duration	Observation (Before Treatment)	Observation (After Treatment)
10/10/2025 to 16/10/2025	<i>Yoni Prakshalan</i> <i>Nimba amrutadi kashayam</i>	7 Days	10/10/2025 -Cystocele present (2 nd degree) - Feeling of mass p/v on exertion present	16/10/2025 -Cystocele absent - Feeling of mass P/v even with exertion absent
10/10/2025 to 12/10/2025	<i>Yoni Pichu</i> <i>Nalpamradi Tailam</i>	3 Days	-Urine incontinence Present	-No urine incontinence
13/10/2025 to 16/10/2025	<i>Yoni Pichu</i> <i>Changeryadi Ghritam</i>	4-7 days	-curdy white discharge present P/V -Lower abdominal heaviness present	- Reduced curdy white discharge -No lower abdominal heaviness.

Obstetric History - G₃ P₃ A₀ L₃

- 1- Female (LSCS)
- 2- Male (LSCS)
- 3- Female (LSCS)

Gynaecological Examination

Per Speculum (P/S) Examination

- Cystocele ++
- Bulge more prominent on coughing
- Vaginal mucosa mild erythematous
- Curdy white discharge++
- Anterior vaginal wall laxity present
- Post-void bulge indicating incomplete bladder emptying

Per Vaginal (P/V) Examination

- Anterior Vaginal wall laxity present
- Cystocele Present (2nd degree), even after post void examination a bulge was still palpable suggesting incomplete bladder emptying.
- Curdy white discharge ++
- Cervix felt low but does not reach the introitus suggestive of 1st degree uterine prolapse.
- Uterus normal in size, anteverted, mobile, non-tender.
- Fornices free and non-tender.

Probable Ayurvedic Diagnosis

Prasamsini Yoni Vyapada (2nd degree Cystocele and 1st degree uterine prolapse)

Follow up 17/10/2025 to 17/11/2025	<i>Chandraprabha vati 1 BD</i> <i>Syrup Neeri 15 ml BD</i> <i>Gandharvahastadi Kashaya</i> <i>15 ml and tab kaishora</i> <i>guggulu 1BD Kegel's</i> <i>Exercise</i>	30 days	- Low back ache present.	- No low back ache
23/11/2025		No any fresh complaints noted		

1. Yoni Prakṣhalana (Vaginal Cleansing)

Purpose: To cleanse vaginal canal, reduce inflammation, eliminate discharge, and enhance tissue tone.

Rationale

Nimbamritadi Kashaya possesses antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and *kapha-pitta* pacifying properties helping to reduce discharge and erythema.

2. Yoni Pichu (Therapeutic Tamponing)

Purpose: To nourish and strengthen vaginal tissues, enhance lubrication, and support pelvic structures.

Medicines Used

- **Day 1–3:** *Nalpamaradi Taila* – indicated for reducing inflammation, soothing tissues, and managing irritation.
- **Day 4–7:** *Changeryadi Ghṛita* – strengthens pelvic tissues, promotes healing, and provides *yonibalya* effect.

DISCUSSION

Prasamsini Yoni Vyapada results primarily from *Apana Vata* dysfunction along with weakness of pelvic tissues. The clinical signs of anterior vaginal wall laxity, incomplete bladder emptying, and urinary dribbling correlate well with cystocele and pelvic floor weakness.

The chosen treatment strategies aimed to

- Improve bladder support
- Reduce discharge and mucosal congestion
- Strengthen vaginal and pelvic tissues
- Restore *vata* balance

The present treatment includes oral medications *Chandraprabha Vati*, *Gandharvahastadi Kashaya*, *kaishora guggulu*, *Syrup Neeri*, along with *Sthanika Chikitsa* like *Yoniprakshalana* with *Nimbamritadi Kashaya*, *Yonipichu* with *Nalpamaradi tailam* and *Changeryadi Ghritam*.

Chandraprabha vati^[3] includes drugs like *Shilajatu*, *Guggulu*, *Triphala*, *Guduchi*, *Bhunimba*, *Trivrutta*, etc, which are *tikta rasa pradhana* and acts as *Pitta-Vata* hara, which have a direct role in *Prasamsini Yonivyapat*. *Shilajatu* acts as *Rasayana* Dravya, it has *Kashaya rasa*, *katu vipaka*, *Natyushnashita veerya*. Its potency gets increased by impregnating it with decoction drugs which alleviate *Vata*, *Pitta* and *Kapha*. *Guggulu* is *Tikta-Katu rasa*, *Ushna Veerya*, *Katu Vipaka*, *Tridosahara* *Prabhava* and mainly works as a *Vatashamaka*. Also, it works as *Vedanasthapana*,

Vranashodhana-ropana. *Chandraprabha Vati* is indicated in *Mutraghat vikara* and it has *Sarvarogapranashini* and *Rasayana* property. It alleviates *Vata*, *Pitta* as well as *Kapha* and promotes strength as well as virility. It works on *Prasamsini Yonivyapat* by its *Rasayana* property, because it will help to reduce muscle laxity and will strengthen the muscle. and nourish and strengthen pelvic muscle.

Kaishora guggulu^[4] include drugs like *Guduchi*, *Guggulu*, *Bibhitaki*, *Haritaki*, *Amalaki*, *Shunthi*, *Maricha*, *pippali*, *Vidanga*, *Trivrutta*, *Danti*, *Goghrita* which are having the unique actions on various health conditions. Ultimate effect is elimination of toxins of degenerative areas, thus promoting more healing and Rejuvenating effects in body. *Kaishora guggulu* help in treat *vatavyadhi* (disease motly related to Bones, Muscles and Nerves etc.) Thus, *Kaishora guggulu* serves as an effective internal medication in the management of back pain and pelvic organ prolapse with its anti-inflammatory, rejuvenating and healing property.

Gandharvahastadi Kashaya^[5] include drugs like *Gandharvahasta*, *Chirbilva*, *Hutasha (chitraka)*, *Vishva*, *Pathya*, *Punarnava*, *Yavasa*, *Bhumittala*. *Gandharvahasta*- as its principal drug, which possesses *Vatahara*, *Anulomana*, and *mridu virechana* properties, help in normalizing the *gati* of *Apana Vata*, relieves colonic dryness and facilitates smooth evacuation of bowel contents. Its *Deepana pachana* action reduces *ama*, thereby improving digestive function and intestinal motility. *Gandharvahastadi Kashaya*, owing to its *Ushna*, *Snigdha* and *Vata-shamaka* properties, alleviates *vata*-include pain and stiffness. By correcting the *Apana Vata* imbalance, the formulation provides relief from backache, lower abdominal heaviness and prevention of disease progression, and improvement in patient comfort.

Syrup Neeri^[6] include drugs like *Gokshura*, *Punarnava*, *Varun*, *Rasna*, *Bhumi Amla*, *Yashitimadhu* *gokghura* and *Punarnava* enhanced diuretic impact without harshness, *Varuna* and *bhumi Amla* targeted support for both urinary passage and renal tissue. *Rasna* and *Yashitimadhu* joint anti – inflammatory and smoothing effect. Its act as natural urinary health tonic and in this condition its help in symptoms of recurrent urination and dribbling of urine.

Sthanika Chikitsa Yoniprakshalan^[7] with *Nimbamritadi Kashaya* *Yoni Prakshalana* or *dhavana* means cleansing process of vagina. It is a cleaning procedure of vagina by medicated

liquid, decoction or water under aseptic precaution. Nimbamritadi Kashaya^[8] which contains drugs like *Nimba*, *Guduchi*, *Vasa*, *Patola*, *Kantakari*, *Musta*, *Kapikachhu*, *Parpataka* and *Shunthi*. All most all drugs have *Tikta- Kashaya Rasa*, *Laghu ruksha guna*, so their action is *srava kleda shoshana*, *Krimighna*, *Shothahara*, *Vrana Shodhana*, *Ropana*, *Vedana Sthapaka*. The predominant Kashaya and *Tikta Rasa* in most of the *Dravyas* help in decreasing the body's excessive *Srava*. The *Ruksha Laghu Guna* of the *Dravyas* helps in *shoshana* of the *Snigdha Guna* of the *Kapha*. *Sheeta Virya* causes *Sthambana*. Usage of lukewarm Kashaya helps in relaxation of muscles along with that it improves the blood supply, venous drainage, lymph supply and activates the local metabolic process which are responsible for the relief of pain tenderness, swelling and stiffness.^[9]

Yonipichu with Nalpamaradi tailam^[10] is a tampon made of sterile cotton swab soaked in *Nalpamaradi tailam* kept to be retained inside the vagina, the formulation comprises a blend of herbal ingredients, including the bark of four species (*Vata*, *Udumbara*, *Ashwatththa*, *Plaksha*), collectively known as *Nalpamara*, along with *Triphala*, *Chandana*, *Kushta*, *Manjishtha*, *Adra Haridra* and *Parpata* all processed in a base of coconut oil (kera Taila). The constituent herbs predominantly exhibit *Kashaya* and *Tikta Rasa*, contributing to the pacification of *pitta* and *kapha* doshas. Their property includes *Sheeta Virya* and *Guru Guna* making the oil particularly beneficial in conditions characterised by inflammation, burning sensations, and skin discolourations.

Yonipichu with Changeryadi Ghritam^[11] is a tampon made of sterile cotton swab soaked in *Changeryadi Ghrita* kept to be retained inside the vagina, till the next micturition. *Changeryadi Ghrita* includes drugs like *Changeri*, *Pippali*, *Nagara*, *Chitraka*, *Gokshur*, *Gajpippali*, *Dhanyaka*, *Bilva*, *Patha*, *Yavani*, *Sarpi* (*Ghrita*), *Dadhi*(curd). These drugs will help in *Prasamsini Yonivyapath* by its *Vatashamaka* property. *Ghrita* itself has a *Pitta-Vata Shamaka Guna*, and because of its *Sanskaranuvartini* property it will also gain the properties of *Changeryadi Dravyas*. And helps in strengthening the pelvic muscles.

CONCLUSION

This case study suggests that Ayurvedic oral medications combined with local therapies such as *Yoni Prakshalana* and *Yoni Pichu* can play a beneficial role in managing *Prasamsini Yoni Vyapada*, particularly in cases with 1st degree uterine prolapse, 2nd degree cystocele and pelvic floor laxity and white discharge per vaginum. The combination of cleansing, anti-inflammatory action, and tissue-strengthening therapies provided measurable symptomatic relief. And change in objective parameters after treatment. This integrated approach not only alleviates symptoms but also strengthens pelvic support structures by addressing the underlying pathology at both

systemic and local levels. Ayurvedic management thus offers a safe, holistic and clinically meaningful alternative for the conservative treatment of early to moderate pelvic organ prolapse, with potential to reduce disease progression and improve quality of life. Further clinical studies with larger sample sizes are recommended to validate these findings.

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